

VALIDATION OF A NOVEL MODEL FOR THE COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF FRP: EXPERIMENTS WITH DIFFERENT FIBRE ORIENTATIONS

T. Bru^{1,2}, R. Olsson¹, G.M. Vyas¹ and S. Costa^{1,2}

¹ Swerea SICOMP, Mölndal, Sweden

Email: thomas.bru@swerea.se, web page: <http://www.swerea.se/sicomp/>

² Chalmers University of Technology, Department of Industrial and Materials Science, Gothenburg, Sweden

Keywords: Crushing, Mechanical testing, Fibre kinking, Fractography, Non-crimp fabric

ABSTRACT

Crush tests have been performed on flat unidirectional non-crimp fabric (NCF) coupons with different fibre orientations as part of the validation of a ply-based damage model for crash. The fibre off-axis angle with respect to the crushing direction ranged from 0° to 90°. The results of the tests indicate that the crush stress remains unchanged for off-axis angles between 0° and 15°. The failure mode in these specimens was out-of-plane kinking. For 20° and 25° off-axis angles the crush stress dropped 20% and evidence of out-of-plane kinking were harder to find. For 45° off-axis angle a network of matrix cracks develops in the specimen and for 90° off-axis angle a brittle shear failure is observed. It is suggested that the out-of-plane kinking is promoted because of the natural waviness of NCF materials and that the high in-plane shear stress generated from 20-25° off-axis loading results in a transition from out-of-plane kinking to in-plane kinking. These hypotheses need, however, to be verified by an extended failure analysis of the crush specimens.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials can offer large improvements in terms of specific energy absorption capabilities in comparison to traditional crash components made of metals. Unfortunately, test methods to study the crushing behaviour of fibre reinforced polymers (FRPs) are lacking, as well as robust numerical methods to predict the physical behaviour.

The computation of large composite structures in crash is extremely expensive because of the level of detail needed to capture the correct failure modes and their interaction during the progressive failure. A common approach to bring down the computation time is to use mesoscale models, i.e. homogenisation of the fibres and the matrix at the ply level. An advantage of mesoscale models over micromechanical models is that the model input can easily be determined from mechanical tests at the ply level. Recently, a novel approach combining a mesoscale continuum damage model (CDM) and a friction model was used to predict the energy dissipation during the progressive compressive failure of FRP plies [1-4]. The model focuses on matrix compressive failure and fibre compressive failure by kinking.

Bru et al. [5] developed a fundamental crush test method to characterise the longitudinal and transverse crushing behaviour of unidirectional (UD) laminates. The present paper is a continuation of this work, as the same setup and non-crimp fabric (NCF) material are used to investigate the influence of the fibre orientation on the crushing response. When the fibres are not aligned with the loading direction, combined shear and compressive stresses are generated, which influence the failure mode. The crushing morphology of specimens with different fibre orientations are correlated with the crush stress extracted during the tests to give a better understanding on the crushing of UD NCFs under off-axis loading. The experimental results presented in this paper will be used for the validation of a mesoscale crash model that is being developed within the same research group [1-4].

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Specimens and crush test set-up

The design of the test specimen and specimen supports, shown in Fig. 1, was optimised for the crushing of 0° -laminates [5]. In order to investigate the effect of the fibre orientation with respect to the crushing direction, specimens were cut in different directions from a UD laminate. The off-axis angle between the fibres and the crushing direction is denoted θ . The off-axis angles investigated are 5° , 10° , 15° , 20° , 25° and 45° . In addition, previous results on longitudinal specimens ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and transverse specimens ($\theta = 90^\circ$) are reported for comparison [1].

Figure 1: Set-up of the crush test and geometry of the specimens.

The laminate used for the study consists of 10 layers of carbon-fibre uni-weave NCF and was infused by resin transfer moulding with LY556 epoxy. Details about the material and manufacturing procedure are published in [6].

The triangular through-thickness trigger shown in Fig. 1 is needed to create a stress concentration and initiate crushing. Before testing, each specimen was scanned on both faces to determine the exact dimension of the trigger. The measurements are reported in Table 1.

The tests were performed under quasi-static conditions in a MTS universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell. Two steel plates with four guiding rods were used to ensure that the crushing plate was perpendicular to the specimen. The specimen was supported at its base to avoid

titling during crushing. The unsupported height (from the trigger tip to top of the support) was between 6 and 7 mm. For some specimens the crushing distance δ was almost as long as the unsupported height, while another group of specimens was only crushed partially inside the trigger. The crushing distance δ was evaluated from optical measurement with a laser between the two steel plates of the test fixture.

	A_0 (mm ²)	δ_{trigger} (mm)	Interval for σ_{cr} meas. (mm)		A_0 (mm ²)	δ_{trigger} (mm)	Interval for σ_{cr} meas. (mm)
$\theta=0^\circ$				$\theta=15^\circ$			
#1	18.5	2.9	0.8–2.8	#4	24.1	3.5	1.0–1.6
#2	19.6	2.8	0.4–2.1	#5	26.6	4.0	0.6–1.7
#3	17.2	3.1	0.7–1.3	#6	21.5	3.3	0.1–1.3
#4	19.3	2.8	0.5–1.4	#7	22.3	2.9	0.1–0.6
#5	23.2	3.3	0.4–1.2	$\theta=20^\circ$			
#6	22.7	3.3	0.3–0.7	#1	26.9	4.5	0.3–1.3
$\theta=5^\circ$				#2	25.8	4.3	0.3–2.7
#1	25.4	3.8	0.4–3.0	#3	25.6	3.9	0.5–2.9
#2	26.3	5.1	0.9–2.7	#4	22.6	3.6	0.2–1.7
#3	25.7	4.7	0.2–2.4	#5	24.9	3.6	0.3–1.7
#4	21.7	3.6	0.3–1.3	#6	23.0	3.6	0.3–1.3
#5	22.2	3.4	0.2–0.6	#7	23.2	3.3	0.3–1.1
#6	18.3	2.8	0.6–1.0	$\theta=25^\circ$			
#7	18.7	2.7	0.2–2.1	#1	22.2	3.3	0.4–1.3
#8	17.3	2.6	0.2–0.7	#2	23.0	3.5	0.4–1.3
$\theta=10^\circ$				$\theta=45^\circ$			
#1	28.5	4.4	0.5–1.5	#1	26.3	3.8	0.3–2.6
#2	28.1	4.1	0.3–2.5	#2	25.9	3.9	0.4–2.8
#3	28.1	4.4	0.4–1.3	#3	26.4	4.7	0.3–3.0
#4	27.9	3.8	0.5–1.2	#4	16.2	2.6	0.5–2.5
#5	23.8	3.9	0.6–1.3	$\theta=90^\circ$			
#6	23.6	3.5	0.8–1.3	#1	17.5	2.9	0.3–2.8
$\theta=15^\circ$				#2	16.8	2.8	0.3–2.4
#1	24.3	4.0	0.3–1.1	#3	19.6	2.9	0.3–2.9
#2	25.1	3.8	0.4–1.2	#4	18.7	3.0	0.4–2.9
#3	24.7	3.6	0.5–1.8				

Table 1: Specimen dimensions and interval selected for the calculation of the crush stress.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Crushing response

A typical load–displacement curve obtained from the tests is shown in Fig. 2. The initial part of the curve is linearly increasing until a sudden load drop at $\delta = 3$ mm. The load is then fluctuating around a constant value. The load drop at $\delta = 3$ mm was associated to the formation of a wedge shape fragment as the crush front approaches the end of the trigger. The wedge originates from cracks growing along the fibres and reaching the free edge of the specimen. Because the wedge is detached from the specimen it simply slides during the continuation of the test without being crushed, as shown in photographs taken at stage (2)–(3) in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Typical load–displacement curve for a specimen crushed over a distance larger than the trigger height.

Figure 3: Morphology of the crush front for a specimen crushed over a distance larger than the trigger height.

Fig. 3 shows a polished cross-section at the mid-width of the specimen. As for all the other micrographs presented in this paper, the specimen was unloaded, potted under vacuum using a

fluorescent epoxy and the polished surface was examined with an optical microscope (Olympus BH2 microscope). Fig. 3 indicates a virtually symmetric failure morphology of the ten plies of the specimen. The innermost plies remained straight and therefore kept a maximum load bearing capability. The resulting failure of these plies is fragmentation. The formation of kink-bands and the accumulation of debris could be observed in the region of the specimen subjected to fragmentation. The plies located further out in the laminate are experiencing outward bending (splaying) during the crushing process. Because of the bending, the splayed plies are losing their load bearing capability and do not fail by kinking and subsequent fragmentation. The failure modes in this part of the specimen are mostly delamination and ply splitting.

Figure 4: Cross-sections of specimens crushed partially in the trigger for different off-axis angles.

The morphology of the crush zone was also observed in tests terminated at a crushing distance equal to half the trigger height. The motivation was to characterise the failure mechanisms involved

during the linear load increase as the trigger is being crushed, i.e. stage (1) in Fig. 2, and to make a qualitative comparison between specimens with different fibre orientations. The results are shown in Fig. 4. A general observation was that the amount of splaying was smaller for the specimens crushed partially inside the trigger than for the specimens crushed along a longer crushing distance. Kink-bands were observed in all specimens with a fibre orientation from 0° to 15° and in some specimens with a 20° and 25° fibre orientation. It is evident from Fig. 4a-b that there is an out-of-plane component in the orientation of the kink-band planes. The influence of uni-weave NCF architecture on the fibre dominated crushing response can clearly be seen in Fig. 4b. On the left side of the crush zone in Fig. 4b, delaminations have initiated from the NCF weft threads and forced several plies to splay without kinking. On the right side, the crush zone is free of weft threads and as a result a kink-band propagates through the specimen thickness. In some of the 20° and 25° off-axis specimens short kink-bands were found in the centre of the crush region (Fig. 4d), although it was not possible to determine the orientation of the kink-band plane. Quite large matrix cracks are visible in the micrographs of 20° and 25° off-axis specimens but they did not develop into a network of cracks as in 45° off-axis specimens (Fig. 5a).

Figure 5: Cross-sections of a specimen with a) a 45° off-axis angle and b) a 90° off-axis angle.

3.2 Average crush stress

Assuming that the failure process is kept within the plane of the laminate and is similar during crushing of the trigger and crushing of the rest of the specimen, the idealised load response must be a linear load increase until the trigger is fully consumed followed by a load plateau at the maximum load. Therefore, the idealised crush stress σ_{cr} must be constant during the entire failure process and can be evaluated from the specimen geometry at any displacement as follows,

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{F}{A(\delta)}, \text{ where } \begin{cases} A(\delta) = A_0 \cdot \delta / \delta_{trigger} & \text{if } \delta \leq \delta_{trigger} \\ A(\delta) = A_0 & \text{if } \delta > \delta_{trigger} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

It was decided to evaluate the crush stress inside the trigger region, i.e. $\delta \leq \delta_{trigger}$, because of the limited amount of splaying at the early stage of the tests. The procedure to evaluate σ_{cr} from the load–displacement curves is shown in Fig. 6. Firstly, an interval is selected from the entire load–

displacement of the specimen. The crushing distance interval was chosen in the region $\delta \leq \delta_{\text{trigger}}$ and in a region that did not include significant load drops which reflects brutal changes in the crushing response. The selected crushing intervals for all specimens are reported in Table 1. Secondly, the crush stress σ_{cr} is evaluated for every δ inside the selected interval according to Eq. 1. The resulting crush stress curve, shown in Fig. 6, is fairly constant thanks to the linear increase of the load and the cross-sectional area $A(\delta)$. Finally, an average of the crush stress is evaluated over the selected crushing interval.

Figure 6: Evaluation of the crush stress from the load–displacement curves during progressive failure of the trigger (one representative specimen is shown for each off-axis angle).

Fig. 7 shows the results of the crush stress evaluation. Taking into account the standard deviation, it can be concluded that the crush stress is the same for a fibre orientation of 0° , 5° , 10° and 15° . For a fibre orientation of 45° and 90° the crush stress is much lower because a different failure mode (transverse compressive failure) is taking place. Transverse compressive failure involves shear failure at an inclined fracture plane parallel to the fibres, Fig. 5b. Kink-band formation is a more efficient energy absorbing failure mechanism in comparison to matrix crack propagation because of the high energy released when breaking the fibres. The crushing stress for large off-axis angles (20° and 25°) is somewhere between the crush stress of small off-axis specimens and the crush stress of 45° off-axis specimens.

Figure 7: Average crush stress as a function of the off-axis angle.

As mentioned earlier, the kink-band planes observed in the micrographs of the crush specimens with small off-axis angles are mostly oriented out-of-plane. The through-thickness direction is the one that requires less energy for a ply to kink because of the natural out-of-plane waviness of the NCF laminate and the lesser support of the ply due to negligible out-of-plane stresses and potential delaminations at the ply interfaces. The shear stresses introduced from the in-plane off-axis loading are not expected to have a strong influence on the out-of-plane kinking mechanism. This explains why the crush stress does not vary for specimens with off-axis angles of 0°, 5°, 10° and 15°.

Figure 8: Evolution of the compressive strength and crush stress with the off-axis angle for HTS45/LY556 material.

Wilhelmsson [7] carried out an experimental investigation on the influence of the off-axis angle on the compressive strength of NCF specimens (using the same material system as the one used in this work). The results are reported in Fig. 8 and are compared with the crush stress measured in this work. Although 2D kinking theory predicts a rapid knock-down of the strength when increasing θ [8], the compressive strength measured experimentally according to the ASTM standards D 3410 and D 6641 [9,10] remained constant for small off-axis angles. The crush stress evolution followed a similar behaviour. For the laminate tested in this work the crush stress was about a third of the compressive strength. For the laminates tested by Wilhelmsson [7] the compressive strength was much lower

because of a higher degree of out-of-plane waviness in the specimens. Wilhelmsson [7] observed the failure morphology of the compressive specimens and reported that kinking was mostly out-of-plane for small off-axis angles, but that a shift towards in-plane kinking was observed in 15° and 20° off-axis specimens. For the crush tests, the drop in stress observed for 20° and 25° off-axis angles might be explained by a similar transition from out-of-plane to in-plane kinking. However, the micrographs of the crush specimens were not conclusive on that matter because the polishing plane selected did not allow the direct observation of the in-plane component of the kink-bands.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A study has been made on the effect of the fibre orientation on the crushing behaviour of UD NCF specimens. The crush stress is not affected by small off-axis angles (5° to 15°) since the failure mode involved is out-plane-kinking. However, for larger off-axis angles (20° and 25°) the measured crush stress drops more than 20 percent. The crush specimens with large off-axis angle presented little or no evidence of out-of-plane kinking failure. Finally, for 45° off-axis crushing a network of matrix cracks develops in the specimen under a combined shear/compression stress state.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The funding for this research from the Swedish Energy Agency (Energimyndigheten), project number 34181-2, is gratefully acknowledged. The authors acknowledge the contribution of MSc student Francisco Silva at Swerea SICOMP in performing some of the mechanical tests.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Gutkin, S.T. Pinho, Combining damage and friction to model compressive damage growth in fibre-reinforced composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **49**, 2015, pp. 2483-2495 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998314549614>).
- [2] R. Gutkin, S. Costa, R. Olsson, A physically based model for kink-band growth and longitudinal crushing of composites under 3D stress states accounting for friction, *Composites Science and Technology*, **135**, 2016, pp. 39-45 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2016.09.002>).
- [3] S. Costa, R. Gutkin, R. Olsson, Mesh objective implementation of a fibre kinking model for damage growth with friction, *Composite Structures*, **168**, 2017, pp. 384-391 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.02.057>).
- [4] S. Costa, R. Olsson, T. Bru, Validation of a novel model for the compressive response of FRP: numerical simulation, *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Composite Materials ICCM-21, Xi'an, China, August 20-25, 2017*.
- [5] T. Bru, P. Waldenström, R. Gutkin, R. Olsson, G.M. Vyas, Development of a test method for evaluating the crushing behaviour of unidirectional laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2017, available online (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998317697811>).
- [6] T. Bru, P. Hellström, R. Gutkin, D. Ramantani, G. Peterson, Characterisation of the mechanical and fracture properties of a uni-weave carbon fibre/epoxy non-crimp fabric composite, *Data in Brief*, **6**, 2016, pp. 680-695 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2016.01.010>).
- [7] D. Wilhelmsson, *On matrix-driven failure in unidirectional NCF composites - A theoretical and experimental study*, Licentiate Thesis, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2016.
- [8] B. Budiansky, N. Fleck, Compressive failure of fibre composites, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **41**, 1993, pp. 183-211 (doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096\(93\)90068-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096(93)90068-Q)).
- [9] ASTM D 3410/ D 3410M – 03(2008). *Standard test method for compressive properties of polymer matrix composite materials with unsupported gage section by shear loading*, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2008.
- [10] ASTM D 6641/ D 6641M – 16e1. *Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials Using a Combined Loading Compression (CLC) Test Fixture*, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2016.